

estimated for PB, SB, SpPB, SpSB, and total spikelets (TSp). Estimates of overall degree and direction of heterosis ($F_{mac_1} - P_{mac}$) were significant and positive for all characters, indicating dominance of higher values.

The values for individual F_1 families, however, differed from the overall estimates for heterosis in different characters (Table 2). The F_1 means deviated conspicuously from the respective parental and midparental values, indicating nonadditive gene action for most characters.

Substantial heterosis in the desirable direction showed in characters like number of PB, SpPB, and TSp, which are related to higher grain yield potential. Most crosses exhibited positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for number of PB and SpPB; however, one Rewa cross, one upland cross, and three glaberrima crosses had negative heterobeltiosis, perhaps because of the already high number of PB and SpPB in the glaberrima parents.

Two Rewa crosses (Rewa 353-

3/IR47705-AC4 and Rewa 353-2/IR30) and three upland crosses (all but IR47705-AC5-1/IR2821143-1-1-2) manifest positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for all characters. The cross Acc. 103995/IR47705-AC4 showed negative heterobeltiosis for SB and SpSB but positive heterobeltiosis for other characters. That is desirable to increase high-density grains ($sp\ gr > 1.20$) and grain yield potential. Most poor grains or low-density grains originated from secondary branches. □

Quality attributes of seed produced on different tillers of IR50

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A bulk seed crop of IR50 was raised during 1987 dry-season (rabi). At the boot leaf stage, 20 plants were marked at random. As panicles emerged, they were numbered sequentially. At harvest, panicles were measured individually for panicle length, number of filled spikelets/tiller, seed weight/tiller, 1,000-grain weight, and germination and vigor before and after 8 d accelerated aging (see table). The vigor index is derived from length of seedling \times germination percentage.

Panicle length and seed attributes among tillers in IR50.

Tiller	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/tiller (no.)		Seed weight/tiller (g)	1000-seed weight (g)	Before aging		After aging	
		Filled	Ill-filled			Germination (%)	Vigor index	Germination (%)	Vigor index
First	20.6	86	12	1.3	20.5	97	3780	39	820
Second	20.5	77	13	1.2	20.4	92	2910	36	730
Third	20.1	76	13	1.1	20.4	90	2650	33	620
Fourth	20.0	71	15	1.1	20.4	88	2380	30	540
Fifth	19.7	68	17	1.0	20.2	80	2100	28	480
Sixth	19.4	63	18	0.9	20.1	77	1920	26	430
Seventh	19.4	60	19	0.9	19.7	75	1820	19	290
Eighth	19.2	56	20	0.8	19.4	68	1500	17	240
Ninth	18.6	51	22	0.7	19.2	60	1230	14	160
Tenth	18.6	49	22	0.7	18.9	52	1050	11	99
Mean	19.6	66	17	0.9	19.9	78	2134	24	440
LSD (P=0.05)	1.1	4	3	0.01	0.1	7.0	192	1	41

Tillers that headed early had higher values for seed quality attributes.

The superior germination and vigor of large, early flowering tillers was evident

in the accelerated aging test. We suggest that only large, early flowering tillers/panicles be used for breeder seed increase. □

A basic plant ideotype for rice

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Plants grow within the confines of horizontal (HS) and vertical (VS) space. HS provides anchorage, VS furnishes solar energy, CO_2 , O, water, and mineral nutrients. Crop productivity depends primarily on the plants' ability to utilize HS and VS.

An efficient plant would be one which occupies the minimum HS, but the maximum VS.

Efficient use of HS by a rice cultivar implies maximum panicles per unit of HS without reduction in mean panicle yield. This requires maximum tillers per unit of HS, with no ineffective tillers, limited tiller mortality, least inter- and intraplant competition, heavy panicles, and minimum intraplant panicle yield variation. Fewer tillers per plant would minimize ineffective tillers and promote intraplant synchrony of flowering, maturity, and panicle yield. Upright growth, erect leaves, and deep roots would minimize intraplant competition.

Taller plants intercept higher amounts

of solar radiation and trap more CO_2 . Thus, taller plants promote better gas exchange between the crop and environment by creating greater humidity within the stand. Greater movement of taller culms in air currents also can improve CO_2 fixation by reducing air-layering. Longer and thicker culms can store more assimilates, up to 40% of which may be transported to the grain. Height should be the optimum to ensure lodging resistance at intended fertility levels and to provide good penetration of sunlight and air movement through the crop stand.

Upright growth with fewer, well-spaced, thick, not-too-short, and stiff leaves should improve penetration of solar radiation as well as free movement of air through the stand. At a constant leaf area index, leaves of taller plants would be spaced farther apart than those of dwarf plants, which should considerably neutralize negative effects of tall stature on sunlight penetration through the canopy. Tall erect rice cultivars are likely to also have deeper roots, to better absorb water and nutrients.

Identification of these morphological traits allows construction of a basic ideotype with characteristic features of taller stature; lodging resistance; upright growth; fewer, all effective tillers; fewer, well-spaced, thick, not-too-short, stiff leaves; heavy panicles; limited intraplant variation in panicle yield; and deep, extensively branched roots. Cultivars of this type would have to be grown at closer spacing.

Rewa 353 (PAU125-1-2/Lalco 14) is our first prototype. It is 130 cm tall, with an average of six very upright, stiff tillers (all effective)/ plant. Highly synchronous panicles yield an average 4 g of long, slender grains. It has <10% sterility and a harvest index of 0.50.

In 1982, Rewa 353 averaged a yield of 4.3 t/ha over 19 locations, compared with 3.85 t/ha for semidwarf check Rasi. In 1983, average yields over 23 locations were 3.5 for Rewa 353 and 2.8 t/ha for Rasi. Both cultivars flower in about 85 d. Although Rewa 353 is an inadequate approximation of the new ideotype, its performance in wider spacings than ideal shows merit. □

Tolerance of 100 indica rice varieties for 2 herbicides. Hangzhou, China.

Reaction ^a	Butachlor	Thiobencarb
Highly tolerant	Long-jiang-dao Radiation 8-1	Long-jiang-dao Wu-jie-gu
Tolerant	B-8 Pioneer 1, Zhen-long 13, Ai-jiao-nan-te, Radiation 85-65, Wu-jie-gu, Xiao-hong-gu, Min-shang 1	B-8 Er-jiu-nan 1, 82-469
Medium tolerant	Er-jiu-lu 1, Ai-nan-zao 1, Ai-nan-zao 39, Lu-hong-zao 1, Tie-lu 17, Xiang-zhu 443 Zhong 834, Zuo 5, Zao-xian 141, 3168-3, Wen 189, Er-jiu-nan 1, 82-469, Qing-lian 16, Wen-ge, IR58, Zhe-fu 802, E-zao 6, Long-fei 313, Er-jiu-ai 7, 60-ri-zao, 70-ri-huo-dao, Qing-gu-ai, Conggui 3, Yin-bu-ai	Er-jiu-lu 1, Ai-nan-zao 1, Ai-nan-zao 39, Lu-hong-zao 1, Tie-lu 17, Xiang-zhu 443 Radiation 8-1, Pioneer 1, Zhen-long 13, Radiation 85-65, Min-shang 1, IR1710
Susceptible	Zhen-shan 97, Si-mei 2, Guang-lu-ai 4, Er-jiu-qing, Zao-jian 1, Jia-xian 785, Zhong 86-151, Gui-lu-ai 8, Wen-guang-qing, Qing-gan-huang, Zhu-xi 26, Nong 8506, Ai-chang 25, PL 15, 15-4, Zhu-yun-nuo, Zao-xian 503, Lian-tang-zao, Zao-lian 31, Xiang-zao-xian 3, Radiation 83-29, BG 367-7, IR54, Dong-hai 109, Tetep, Cong-gui 314, Guang-liu-zao Bao-nan-zao, IR29, Qing-xiao-jin-zao, Zhong 84-86, Zhen-gui 51, Yuan-feng-zao, Er-jiu-feng, Zao-er-liu 14, Chuan 84-508, Shu-feng 1, Zhen-lu-xi 1, Cong-xie 39, Guang-er-ai 105, Guang-hong 40, IR22, IR22107, IR1710	Zhen-shan 97, Si-mei 2, Guang-lu-ai 4, Er-jiu-qing, Zao-jian 1, Jia-xian 785, Zhong 86-151, Gui-lu-ai 8, Wen-guang-qing, Qing-gan-huang, Zhu-xi 26, Nong 8506, Ai-chang 25, PL 15, 15-4, Zhu-yun-nuo, Zao-xian 503, Lian-tang-zao, Zao-lian 31, Xiang-zao-xian 3, Radiation 83-29, BG 367-7, IR54, Dong-hai 109, Tetep, Cong-gui 314, Guang-liu-zao Ai-jiao-nan-te, Zhong 83-4, Zuo 5, 3168-3, Wen 189, Qing-lian 16, E-zao 6, Long-fei 313, Er-jiu-ai 7, 70-ri-huo-dao, Qing-gu-ai, Cong-gui 3, Yin-bu-ai, Zao-feng-shou, Yin-zao 41 1, Zhu-ke 2, Hong 410, IR26
Highly susceptible	Fu-yu 1, Zhe 85-2, Wen-xuan-qing, L201, L202, IR24, IR30, 5010, Zhu-lian-ai, B3, IR50, Yuan-wu, Chun-feng 1, Zhai-ye-qing 8, IR9129, Hua-ai 837 Zao-feng-shou, Yin-zao 411, Zhu-ke 2, Hong 410, IR26	Fu-yu 1, Zhe 85-2, Wen-xuan-qing, L201, L202, IR24, IR30, 5010, Zhu-lian-ai, B3, IR50, Yuan-wu, Chun-feng 1, Zhai-ye-qing 8, IR9129, Hua-ai 837 Xiao-hong-gu, Zao-xian 141, Wen-ge, IR58, Zhe-fu 802, 60-ri-zao, Bao-nan-zao, IR29, Qing-xiao-jin-zao, Zhong 84-86, Zhen-gui 51, Yuan-feng-zao, Er-jiu-feng, Zao-er-liu 14, Chuan 84-508, Shu-feng 1, Zhen-lu-xi 1, Cong-xie 39, Guanger-ai 105, Guang-hong 40, IR22, IR22107

^aHighly tolerant: 2d and 3d leaves normal; tolerant: 2d leaf partially with water-soaked light brown spots, 3d normal; medium tolerant: 2d leaf with many large light brown spots, 3d with some; susceptible: spots linked with each other, leaves partially necrotic; highly susceptible: seedlings nearly dead or dead.

A technique for screening herbicide tolerance in rice

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We developed a technique to evaluate indica rices for herbicide tolerance at the seedling stage. To speed up screening for herbicide tolerance, we used the

treatment method commonly applied in the field on seedlings in the incubator.

Seedlings were grown in 50- × 20- × 15-cm plastic trays with 7-cm-deep soil. At the 2-leaf stage, different trays were flooded with 50, 100, and 500 ppm butachlor, and 250, 500, and 1,000 ppm thiobencarb up to the pulvinus of the second leaf, with water treatment as a

check. Seedlings were kept in the incubator (30/25 °C day/night, 12 h light and 3000 lx/d) for 11 d.

Treatment with 100 ppm butachlor or 500 ppm thiobencarb was best for discriminating herbicide tolerance among varieties. In most varieties, tolerance for both herbicides was similar (correlation coefficient 0.67**).